

A Study on Password Breaking Tools

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Abstract: In this paper, there is brief description of the tool CHNTPW. CHNTPW is a KALI LINUX tool used to reset local Windows password that we used to take access over the Windows system. CHNTPW is a simple tool that usually works by deleting the SAM file that is existing in the local system config folder. SAM file is the database file for storing the password hashes.

On advance research we would be comparing on CHNTPW with other password breaking tools. The comparisons can be made based on the different ability of the tools to break or reset the password available.

Keywords: CHNTPW, SAM file, Password Resetting.

I. INTRODUCTION

CHNTPW is a KALI LINUX tool for resetting or blanking local passwords used in WindowsNT, 2000, XP, Vista, 7, 8, 8.1 and 10. It is done by editing the SAM file in the database where the Windows stores password hashes. The ways to use the program is via installing the CHNTPW as a package available in most modern Linuxdistributions. CHNTPW does not support for fully encrypted NTFS partitions (that only possible for exceptions to this are encrypted partitions readable by Linux such as LUKS), the usernames containing Active Directory passwords, or Unicode characters (which includes the exception of local users of systems whom the members of an AD domain). The changing password feature would not be fully functional, so blanking the password is mostly recommended (in fact for latter versions of Windows that's the only possible option). The CHNTPW can be easily installed on a local host device with required a bootable USB loaded with the KALI LINUX O.S. After the installation the CHNTPW can be easily accessed in the command prompt through the piece of code and listing the needed files over the prompt. The CHNTPW makes use of the Security Account Manager (SAM) file to access the local password.

SAM FILE

The Security Account Manager (SAM), is always a database file for storing the local hashes and passwords found in Windows XP, Windows Vista, Windows 7, 8.1 and 10. It is used to authenticate local and remote users. The SAM file is most protected file in the Windows OS which cannot be accessed directly in the system without any root. The SAM file is found at the location /Windows/System32/config. The passwords in the SAM are stored in hashed format which is not easy to decode down to normal form.

PASSWORD RESETTING

This password resetting can be done by gaining physical access to the target machine. If somebody gains access over the target machine for a small moment of time, they should be able to copy the password hashes from the SAM file. This could be considered as a very stealthy attack and difficult to be detected. This sometimes is inappropriate that the penetration tester would leave few clues that they accessed the target machine. Remember the penetration tester can copy the password but it will take its own time for cracking it and finding the original password.

Another way of password resetting is to gain physical access over the target machine and completely root the system in order to access the SAM file and completely delete the file from the system folder. This will completely reset the password of the system. There after there won't be any password for login the system.

Both the steps are hard in normal concerns, but can only be possible by a penetration tester to access the target machine with ease. For normal people it could be a tough job to make an easy access over the target machine. The research work is based on the easy way of password resetting the local windows password by any of them.

The password resetting is done here by using the Kali Linux OS with the help of a tool CHNTPW that can be done by simply listing the administrator files and accessing the SAM file. After the complete access there is a option for delete the SAM file permanently.

II. WORKING CONCEPTS

Steps for resetting windows password,

STEP 1: Load a Bootable Kali OS. Download KALI LINUX OS and burn to CD/DVD or make a bootable USB loaded with the OS.

STEP 2: Completely Restart the Machine. Restart the Windows OS as it does not completely shut down. Instead it hibernates and when it boots again, it reloads to initial state. This could speed up the Starting- Up Process.

STEP 3: Enter to Kali Linux. After the restart go to boot menu and initialize the KALI LINUX. When it loads then will open the terminal window.

STEP 4: Mount Windows OS Drive. Right Click on the Drive and Open a terminalwindow

Fig 2.1 Open the Terminal

STEP 5: Open SAM File. The SAM file is located at the /Windows/System32/config.

Fig 2.2 Open the SAM file location

STEP 6: Listing all Users in SAM file. Run the command “chntpw -l SAM” and it will list out all the usernames stored in the local Windows System

Fig 2.3 List the USERS in SAM

STEP 7: Select the User. After listing select the required Username that to be modified by simply running the command chntpw -u “USERNAME” SAM.

Fig 2.4 Select the needed USER

Step 8: Select the option. After selecting the user a list of options will be listed, in which the option to clear the user password to be selected.

Fig 2.5 Select the required option

The password will be cleared when we logged at next time.

III. OTHER ALTERNATIVE TOOLS

As the CHNTPW is used in the case where the local Windows password have to be blanked or reset. The alternative tools that can be used in place of CHNTPW are:

- OPHCRACK
- JOHN THE RIPPER

OPHCRACK:

Ophcrack is a free open-source (GPL licensed) program that cracks windows login and other passwords by using LM hashes through the rainbow tables. The program includes the ability to import the hashes from a variety of formats, including dumping directly from the SAM files of Windows. The ophcrack can crack most passwords available within a small amount of time.

The Ophcrack works on the local password management by cracking the hash files that are gained by the rainbow tables to access the windows files such as the SAM files that doesn't have the direct user access.

JOHN THE RIPPER:

John the ripper is a password cracking tool. It was developed for the Unix operating system. It is among the most frequently used password testing and breaking programs as it combines a number of other password breaking tools together that helps to detect the password hashes and helps to crack the hash.

It can be easily work against any type of encrypted password formats including several crypt password hash types most commonly found on various Unix versions. So the John the Ripper is an advanced level of password cracking tool and can be easily used for penetrating into the system Passwords.

John the ripper is a most advanced level password cracking tool that quickly decrypts the hash files to simplest form in a command prompt execution.

IV. COMPARATIVE DISCUSSION

The research work had been done on the windows operating system where the login password is stored as hashes in SAM file. The SAM is the Security Account Manager which is the location..

C:\windows\System32\config\SAM file>

The SAM file is not accessible by any user directly which is highly secured in provided area.

The tools Ophcrack and John the ripper are password breakers that means they can decrypt the password if the Hash file is gained. For which other tools are important to

access the hash file.

OPHCRACK

The Ophcrack uses the rainbow tables which are the pre-computed list of hash values for every possible combination of characteristics.

Ophcrack tool can easily access the SAM file using the PWDUMP file access and generates the SAM file. After getting the hash the decryption is very easy in the tool.

On comparing with CHNTPW there is no possibility of getting the password stored in the SAM but instead it permanently deletes the SAM file and it blanks the password.

John The Ripper

John the ripper is the most widely used password cracker. The John the ripper cannot access the SAM file. It have to access the hash file using other tools. After gaining the hash file it can easily decrypt the hash file stored in the .txt file and generate the password.

On comparing with CHNTPW there is no possibility of getting the password stored in the SAM but instead it permanently deletes the SAM file and it blanks the password.

Both the tools OPHCRACK and JOHN THE RIPPER can only be able to crack if we have access to windows. If the password login is not possible then its not even worth to used these tools.

So in such case CHNTPW is very useful as it requires only a Kali Linux O S in the local system. Then it can list all the users in the system administration and get access the SAM file. After getting the file there is an option to delete the SAM file as it removes the password.

V. CONCLUSION

CHNTPW is a password cracker tool to crack windows user account password. Using this utility one can erase the password of the windows user account. This Tool can drag under both Ethical Hacking and Password cracking. CHNTPW helps to retrieves information like accounts, account types, password hashes etc from the SAM. The tool can alter the values present in SAM to reset the password or to change it. This tool is also known as SAM password recovery utility, since it modifies the SAM File.

VI. REFERENCES

- [1] Mohd Ehmer, Khan, and Farmeena, Khan, (2012), "A comparative study of white box, black box and grey box testing techniques".
- [2] Andrew Kerney, Zuehlke, (2017), "An Analysis of Tools, Techniques, and Mathematics Involved in a Penetration Test".
- [3] Jai Narayan, Goel and Asghar, Mohsen Hallaj and Kumar, Vivek and Pandey, Sudhir Kumar, (2016), "Ensemble based approach to increase vulnerability assessment and penetration testing accuracy".
- [4] Deris, Stiawan and Mohammad, Yazid Bin Idris and Abdul, Hanan Abdullah and Mohammed, AlQurashi and Rahmat, Budiarto. (2016),

“Penetration Testing and Mitigation of Vulnerabilities Windows Server”.

- [5] Nirnay, Ghosh and Ishan, Chokshi and Mithun, Sarkar and Soumya, K Ghosh and Anil, Kumar Kaushik and Sajal, K Das, (2015), "Netsecuritas: An integrated attack graph-based security assessment tool for enterprise networks".
- [6] Aleatha, Shanley & Michael, N Johnstone, (2017), "Selection of penetration testing methodologies: A comparison and evaluation".
- [7] Mohammed Farik, (2017), “Cracking Advanced Standard Encryption” based on the password cracking using the tools like John The Ripper.